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Research Article

**PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING AND PHYTOCHEMICAL
EVALUATION OF ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY OF
DIOSPYROS PEREGRINA IN STREPTOZOTOCIN INDUCED
DIABETIC RATS****Pragna Dasaram *, Murali Sollu , Gampa Vijaykumar**Department of Pharmacology, KGR Institute Of Technology and Management, Rampally (v),
Keesara (m), Ranga Reddy (d), Telangana.**Abstract:**

Diabetes mellitus is a most common endocrine disorder, affecting more than 300 million people worldwide. For these therapies developed along the principles of allopathic are often limited in efficacy, Carry the risk of adverse effects, and are often too costly, especially for the developing world. To evaluate antidiabetic activity of Diospyros peregrine in streptozotocin (STZ) induced diabetes in albino rats albino rats were randomly divided into six groups (n=6). Diabetes was induced 16hrs intraperitoneal injection. After acute toxicity test, the Swiss albino mice were induced with streptozotocin (STZ) to get experimental diabetes animals. The fasting mean blood glucose level before and after treatment for normal, diabetic untreated and diabetic mice treated with aqueous and 70% ethanol extracts were performed. Data were statistically evaluated by using Statistical Package

The acute oral toxicity studies of the extracts revealed no toxic effects up to the levels of 2000mg/kg b.wt. The aqueous and Methanolic extracts of 20 and 30mg/kg body weight of Diospyros peregrine was screened for the presence of hypoglycemic and antidiabetic activity. In this study diabetes was induced by a single IP dose streptozotocin (STZ) in 72hrs fasted rats. The FBGL was carried on 7th, 14th and 21st day and OGTT was measured on 8th, 15th and 22nd day. Glibeclamide was taken as the standard and the results are quite comparable with it. The studies were indicated that the leaves of Diospyros peregrine are effective in regeneration of insulin secreting β -cells and thus possess antidiabetic activity. The aqueous and Methanolic extracts showed significant effect in decreasing the Fasting blood Glucose level and oral glucose tolerance test of rats and it's also showed good hypoglycemic activity in normal glycemic rats. The preliminary phytochemical analysis of the extracts of Diospyros peregrine revealed the presence of Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Steroids, Tannins, Anthraquinones, Terpenoids and Cardiac glycoside as the possible biologically active principles.

Keywords: *Diospyros peregrine, streptozotocin (STZ), Glibenclamide, FBGL and OGTT.*

Corresponding author:

Pragna Dasaram *,
Department of Pharmacology,
KGR Institute of Technology and Management,
Rampally (V), Keesara (M), Telangana.
Email Id- dasarampragna@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

1.1-Diabetes Mellitus (DM):

Diabetes is one of the most common non-communicable diseases and a serious life-long condition appearing worldwide. The etiology of diabetes is a complex interaction of genetic and environmental factors. It is a heterogeneous group of metabolic disorders characterized physiologically by dysfunction of pancreatic beta cells and deficiency in insulin secretion or insulin activity and clinically by hyperglycemia or impaired glucose tolerance and other manifestable disorders. It is an endocrinological syndrome abnormally having high levels of sugar in the blood. This may be either due to insulin not being produced at all, is not made at sufficient levels, or is not as effective as it should be.

Diabetes is still a serious health problem all over the world since it is associated with increased morbidity and mortality rate. When compared with the general population, mortality and morbidity increase in diabetes is mainly due to the associated chronic complications both specific (microvascular) and nonspecific (macrovascular). Since the disease prevails in both genders and in all age groups, the general public has a concern about its control and treatment¹.

1.2-Classification of DM

Diabetes is classified by underlying cause. The most common forms of diabetes are categorized as

Type 1, or insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM) - an autoimmune disease in which the body's own immune system attacks the pancreatic beta cells, rendering it unable to produce insulin and

Type 2, or non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM) - in which there is resistance to the effects of insulin or a defect in insulin secretion.

Type 2 diabetes commonly occurs in adults associated with obesity. There are many underlying factors that contribute to the high blood glucose levels in these individuals. An important factor is the resistance to insulin in the body essentially ignoring its insulin secretions. A second factor is the decreased production of insulin by the cells of the pancreas. Therefore, an individual with Type 2 diabetes may have a combination of deficient secretion and deficient action of insulin. In contrast to Type 2 diabetes, Type 1 diabetes most commonly occurs in children and is a result of the body's immune system attacking and destroying the beta cells. The trigger for this autoimmune attack is not clear, but the result is the end of insulin production².

Multiple risk factors for the development of Type 2

diabetes mellitus³:

- Family history (parents with diabetes).
- Obesity (i.e., $\geq 20\%$ over ideal body weight or body mass index $\geq 25\text{kg/m}^2$).
- Habitual physical inactivity.
- Impaired glucose tolerance.
- Hypertension ($\geq 140/90\text{mm Hg}$ in adults).
- High density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol $\leq 35\text{mg/dl}$ and/or triglyceride level $\geq 250\text{mg/dl}$.

1.3-History

The term "Diabetes" was first used around 250 B.C. It is a Greek word meaning "to syphon", reflecting how diabetes seemed to rapidly drain fluid from the affected individual. The Greek physician Aretaeus noted that affected individuals passed increasing amounts of urine as if there was "liquefaction of flesh and bones into urine". The complete term "diabetes mellitus" was coined in 1674 by Thomas Willis. Mellitus is Latin for honey, which is how Willis described the urine of diabetics⁵.

Historical accounts reveal that as early as 700-200 BC, diabetes mellitus was a well recognized disease in India and was even distinguished as two types, a genetically based disorder and other one resulting from dietary indiscretion. Ancient Hindu writings document how black ants and flies were attracted to the urine of diabetics. The Indian physician Sushruta in 400 B.C. described the sweet taste of urine from affected individuals, and for many centuries to come, the sweet taste of urine was a key to the diagnosis.

Physicians have observed the effects of diabetes for thousands of years. One of the effects of diabetes is the presence of glucose in the urine (glucosuria). For much of the time, little was known about this fatal disease that caused weight loss of body, extreme thirst, and frequent urination. It was in 1922 that the first patient was successfully treated with insulin. Till the mid-1800s, the treatments offered for diabetes varied tremendously. A breakthrough in the puzzle of diabetes came in 1889. German physicians Joseph von Mering and Oskar Minkowski surgically removed the pancreas from dogs. The dogs immediately developed diabetes. Now that a link was established between the pancreas and diabetes, research focused on isolating the pancreatic extract that could treat diabetes. Dr. Frederick Banting succeeded in his experiments of isolating a pancreatic extract. The diabetic dog was kept alive for eight days by regular injections until supplies of the extract, at that time called "isletin", was exhausted. Experiments on dogs showed that extracts from the pancreas caused a drop in blood sugar, caused glucose in the urine to disappear, and produced a marked improvement in clinical condition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The designing of methodology involves a series of steps taken in a systematic way in order to achieve the set goal(s) under the prescribed guidelines and recommendations. It includes in it all the steps from field trip to the observation including selection and collection of the medicinal plant, selection of dose value, standardization of protocol, usage of instruments, preparation of reagents, selection of specific solvents for extraction, formation of protocols and final execution of the standardized protocol. All this requires good build of mind and a good and soft technical hand to handle the materials and procedure in a true scientific manner.

Drugs and Chemicals

Drugs and Chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade and of highest purity procured from standard commercial sources in India.

Table No: 6.1 Drugs and Chemicals

<i>S.No</i>	<i>Materials</i>	<i>Company Name</i>
1.	Streptozotocin (STZ)	Quali Kems Fine Chem Pvt, Ltd, Vadodara.
2.	Methanol	Merck, India.
3.	Alcohol	Merck, India.
4.	Glibenclamide	Orchid Pharma Ltd, Chennai.

Instruments

Following instruments were required for the study:

Table No: 6.2- List of Instruments used for study

<i>Name of the instrument</i>	<i>Source</i>
Centrifuge	Dolphin
Digital weighing balance	Horizon
Glucometer	Horizon
Heating mantle	ASGI®
Refrigerator	Videocon
Soxhlet extractor	ASGI®
Condenser	ASGI®
Burette stand	Dolphin
Round bottom flask	ASGI®, Amar
Mixer	Videocon
Oven	ASGI®
Water bath	ASGI®
Stirrer/glass rod	ASGI®
Watch glass	ASGI®
Whatmann filter paper	Manipore microproducts, Ghaizabad.
Butter paper	ASGI®
Spatula	ASGI®
Rubber pipes	ASGI®

Experimental animals

Healthy adult albino wistar rats weighing 200-250grams of either sex were selected for the study. Animals were housed in appropriate cages in uniform hygienic conditions and fed with standard pellet diet (Amrul Laboratory Animal Diet) and water ad libitum. They were fasted overnight before the day of experiment, after 72hours of fasting from the day of streptozotocin introduction. Animals were housed within the departmental animal house and the room temperature was maintained at 27° C. Animal studies had approval of IAEC.

Plant Material Collection

The leaves of *Diospyros peregrine* was collected from the local market in Hyderabad in the month of January and was identified and authenticated from Department of Pharmacognosy. The plant material was cleaned, reduced to small fragments, air dried under shade at room temperature and coarsely powdered in a mixer. The powdered material was stored or taken up for extraction process.

Preparation of plant extracts:**Preparation of Aqueous Extract:**

Dried leaves of *Diospyros peregrine* were taken about 20gms into 250ml beaker containing 200ml of water. The contents were mixed well and then the mixture was boiled up to 80-90°C for 4-5hrs. Further the extract was filtered with whatmann filter paper. The filtrate was boiled until the concentrated residue is formed. The concentrated product was sealed in sample covers and stored under room temperature and used for further experiment to check the activities.

Preparation of Methanolic Extract:

Dried leaves of *Diospyros peregrine* were taken about 20gms into 250ml beaker containing 200ml of Methanolic. The contents were mixed well and then the mixture was boiled up to 50-60°C for 4-5hrs. Further the extract was filtered with whatmann filter paper. The filtrate was boiled until the concentrated residue is formed. The concentrated product was

sealed in sample covers and stored under room temperature and used for further experiment to check the activities.

Selection of dose for animal study

The dose considered for the experiment on rats was obtained from conversion of human dose of *Diospyros peregrine* (3-5 g/kg). The conversion factor of human dose (per 200 g body weight) is 0.018 for rats (Ghosh 1984). Hence the calculated dose for the rats (considering human dose 0.3 and 0.5 g/kg) is 20 and 30 mg/kg. Acute toxicity was done at dose of 2000mg/kg body weight.

Pharmacological evaluation**Preparation of extracts:**

The aqueous and Methanolic extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* suspended in water in presence of 3%v/v Tween-80 solution.

All the drugs were administered orally for experimental purpose. Each time preparations of the extracts were prepared when required. The drugs were administered at a constant volume of 10ml/kg for each animal.

ACUTE ORAL TOXICITY:

The acute oral toxicity of aqueous and Methanolic extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* was determined by using Albino Wistar rats (200-250g) which were maintained under standard conditions. The animals were fasted 12 hour prior to the experiment, up and down procedure OECD guideline no. 425 were adopted for toxicity studies. Animals were administered with single dose of individual extract up to 2000mg/kg and observed for its mortality during 2days and 7days study period (short term) toxicity and observed up to 7days for their mortality, behavioral and neurological profiles.

Assessment of Anti-diabetic Activity in Normal and Alloxan induced Rats**Assessment of hypoglycemic activity on normal rats.****Table----.Group Classification:**

Group	Treatment	Dose(mg/kg)
Group 1	Normal control received distilled water	10ml/kg
Group 2	Standard group received Glibenclamide	10ml/kg
Group 3	Aqueous extract of <i>Diospyros peregrine</i>	20 mg/kg
Group 4	Aqueous extract of <i>Diospyros peregrine</i>	30 mg/kg
Group 5	Methanolic extract of <i>Diospyros peregrine</i>	20 mg/kg
Group 6	Methanolic extract of <i>Diospyros peregrine</i>	30 mg/kg

Procedure:

Animals were divided randomly into six groups of four and each was fasted to overnight. The blood samples were withdrawn by tail vein at 0 hour i.e. before I.P administration of extracts/standard/vehicle. Then blood was collected at an interval of 1, 2, 4, and 8 hour after the administration on 0th, 7th, 14th and 21st day respectively according to procedure blood glucose levels were measured by glucometer (ONE TOUCH glucometer).

➤ **Oral glucose tolerance test(OGTT) in normal rats:**

On the next day (1st, 8th, 15th and 22nd day) after the assessment of hypoglycemic activity OGTT was carried out in same normal animals.

Procedure:

All the animals in each group were administered 2g/kg of glucose one hour after extract/ glibenclamide/ vehicle administration. The blood samples were collected by tail vein at 0 hour, 0.5 hour, 1 hour, 1.5 hour and 2 hour after the administration of glucose load. Blood glucose levels were measured by glucometer on 1st, 8th, 15th and 22nd day respectively.

Assessment of Anti-Diabetic Activity in streptozotocin (STZ) Induced Diabetic Rats:

Induction of Diabetes:

Albino Wistar rats of either sex weighing 200-250 g were selected for the study. All the animals were allowed free access to water and pellet diet and maintained at room temperature in rat cages.

streptozotocin (STZ) was dissolved in normal saline immediately before use. Diabetes was induced in 16 hour fasted rats by single intraperitoneal injection of 120 mg/kg body weight of freshly prepared alloxan in normal saline.

The rats after were given 5% w/v glucose solution in feeding bottles for next 24 hours in their cages to prevent hypoglycemia. After 72 hours rats with fasting blood glucose levels greater than 200 mg/dl were selected and used for further studies

All the animals were observed for seven days for consistent hyperglycemia (fasting blood glucose level greater than 200 mg/dl and lesser than 400 mg/dl) and such animals were selected and divided into six groups of four each and used for the study of the following experimental models.

Table. Group Classification:

Group	Treatment	Dose(mg/kg)
Group 1	Normal control received distilled water	10ml/kg
Group 2	Diabetic control received distilled water	10ml/kg
Group 3	Standard group received Glibenclamide	10ml/kg
Group 4	Aqueous extract of <i>Diospyros peregrine</i>	20mg/kg
Group 5	Aqueous extract of <i>Diospyros peregrine</i>	30mg/kg
Group 6	Methanolic extract of <i>Diospyros peregrine</i>	20 mg/kg
Group 7	Methanolic extract of <i>Diospyros peregrine</i>	30 mg/kg

Effect of Aqueous and Methanolic extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on blood glucose levels in streptozotocin (STZ) induced diabetic rats:

All the animals of above groups were administered as per treatment protocol mentioned above. The blood samples were collected by retro orbital puncture at 0,1,2,4 and 8 hour after the administration. The treatment was continued for next 22 days. Again blood samples were also collected on 7th, 14th and 21st day after 1 hour administration for sub acute study. Blood glucose level was measured by glucometer at various time intervals.

Oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) in streptozotocin (STZ) induced diabetic rats:

On the 8th, 15th and 22nd day OGTT was carried out on the same alloxan induced diabetic animals used for assessment of anti-diabetic activity studies.

Procedure:

All the animals in each group were administered 2g/kg of glucose one hour after extract/ Glibenclamide/ vehicle administration. The blood samples were collected by retro orbital puncture at 0 hour, 0.5 hour, 1 hour, 1.5 hour and 2 hour after the administration of the glucose load. The Blood samples were collected by tail vein and its blood glucose levels were measured by using a glucometer apparatus.

Statistical analysis

The values were expressed as mean \pm SEM data was analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by T-test. Two sets of comparison had made. i.e.

1. Normal control Vs All treated groups.

2. Diabetic Control Vs All treated groups. Differences between groups were considered significant at $P < 0.001$ and $P < 0.05$ levels.

RESULTS

Phytochemical screening of *Diospyros peregrine*

The present investigation concluded that the isolated compounds from the plant *Diospyros peregrine* shows

the various Pharmacological effects was determined due to the presence of different phytochemical compounds. Further study is needed for the isolation of the constituents present in the plant and its individual pharmacological activity should need to consider and ultimately it should be implemented for the benefit to human beings.

Table: Phytochemical screening of *Diospyros peregrine*.

S.No.	Phytoconstituents	Aqueous	Methanolic
1.	Alkaloids	+	+
2.	Flavonoids	-	+
3.	Steroids	-	+
4.	Tannins	-	+
5.	Anthraquinones	-	+
6.	Terpenoids	+	-
7.	Cardiac glycoside	-	+
8.	Saponins	+	+

HYPOGLYCEMIC ACTIVITY IN NORMAL RATS

Fasting Blood Glucose Levels (FBGL) were within the range of 90-105 mg/dl in all the groups at 0day. Repeated treatment with the doses of aqueous and Methanolic extract (100 and 200 mg/kg) significantly decrease the blood glucose level on 7th, 14th and 21st day, indicating that the extract produce significant hypoglycemic activity after repeated administration.

Glibenclamide (10mg/kg) also significantly reduced Fasting Blood Glucose Level (FBGL) after repeated administration as compare to normal control group. Changes in FBGL in different groups after repeated dose administration are summarized in Table.

Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on fasting blood glucose level (FBGL) in normal rats

Table No: 7.2- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on fasting blood glucose level (FBGL) in normal rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level (mg/dl)		
		7 th day	14 th day	21 st day
Normal control	-	90.21±2.51	78.10±1.30	68.36±2.14
Glibenclamide	10	85.06±5.12	77.19±4.41	68.11±5.19
AQEDP1	20	89.05±3.93	84.03±9.06	74.11±2.15
AQEDP2	30	83.25±1.50	75.06±1.25	70.92±1.50
MEDP1	20	78.86±3.62	63.36±0.11	59.65±4.62
MEDP2	30	84.3±5.20	72.15±0.30	67.81±3.29

Values are expressed as mean± S.E.M. n=6. Significant values were compared with $p < 0.005$, normal control Vs all groups. Parent thesis indicates % reduction in BGL.

Figure: - Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on fasting blood glucose level (FBGL) in normal rats.

➤ **Oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) -**

Both the aqueous and Ethanolic extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* significantly ($P<0.005$) suppress the rise in FBGL after glucose load (2g/kg) in rats, at first half-an-hour and up to 2hr time period as compare with other groups extract Glibenclamide on 8th, 15th and 22nd day. While aqueous and Methanolic extracts produced significant reduction in FBGL. Glibenclamide (10mg/kg) showed ($P<0.005$) significant suppression in FBGL rise at first half-an-hour, 1hr and normalized FBGL within 2hr. The detailed results are summarized in Table No.

Table No:Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 8th, 15th and 22nd day in normal rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level(mg/dl)		
		8 th day	15 th day	22 nd day
Normal control	-	82.03±0.41	89.00±3.14	91.62±0.06
Glibenclamide	10	78.60±1.30	72.16±0.50	68.06±2.55
AQEDP1	20	81.92±3.09	80.25±1.93	74.96±1.34
AQEDP2	30	75.46±2.24	71.30±0.24	70.25±3.92
MEDP1	20	80.22±1.30	76.29±3.11	67.10±4.36
MEDP2	30	70.32±0.20	64.55±2.31	58.59±5.65

Values are expressed as mean ± S.E.M. n=6. Significant values were compared with $P<0.005$. Normal control Vs all groups. Paranthesis indicates % reduction in BGL.

Figure:- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 8th, 15th and 22nd day in normal rats.

Table No:- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 22nd day in normal rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level(mg/dl) 22 nd day			
		0.5 hour	1 st hour	1.5 hour	2 nd hour
Normal control	-	47.18±1.24	69.1±2.11	87.24±2.90	92.31±2.93
Glibenclamide	10	41.38±2.18	67.28±1.10	70.28±5.17	70.21±1.50
AQEDP1	20	51.19±1.28	65.34±1.01	78.54±1.42	76.17±4.75
AQEDP2	30	58.01±3.12	63.22±3.56	68.39±2.14	71.57±2.26
MEDP1	20	60.58±1.35	65.26±2.14	72.15±0.78	70.38±3.76
MEDP2	30	38.15±3.57	46.25±1.35	52.23±1.28	60.61±1.65

Figure 7.8:- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 22nd day in normal rats

ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY IN ALLOXAN INDUCED DIABETIC RATS

➤ Effect of *Diospyros peregrine* extracts on antidiabetic activity in alloxan induced diabetic rats

The animals treated with 100 and 200mg/kg of aqueous and Methanolic of different extracts shown significant decrease ($P<0.05$) in FBGL on 7th, 14th and 21st day of treatment when compare to other groups of animals. The aqueous extracts have reduced more (%) in FBGL when compared to Methanolic extracts except standard group. The detailed results are summarized in Table.

Table No: Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on fasting blood glucose level (FBGL) in Alloxan induced diabetic rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level (mg/dl)		
		7 th day	14 th day	21 st day
Normal control	-	76.36±9.69	80.14±3.12	81.62±2.62
Diabetic control	10	292.52±93.05	265.33±2.12	248.02±1.05
Glibenclamide	10	260.19±15.16	242.12±6.62	228.50±0.15
AQEDP1	20	371.73±39.21	356.32±9.90	330.11±9.12
AQEDP2	30	378.50±42.34	362.11±1.28	341.13±3.30
MEDP1	20	290.99±02.09	270.20±4.43	220.92±5.29
MEDP2	30	201.34±15.19	185.14±6.26	156.30±2.21

Values are expressed as mean ± S.E.M. n=6. Significant values were compared with $P<0.05$. Normal control Vs all groups. Paranthesis indicates % reduction in BGL.

Figure: Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on fasting blood glucose level (FBGL) in Alloxan induced diabetic rats.

➤ **Oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) on 8th, 15th and 22nd day-**

Both the aqueous and Methanolic extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* are significantly ($P < 0.05$) suppress the rise in FBGL after glucose load (2g/kg) in rats, at first half-an-hour and up to 2hr time period as compare with other groups extract Glibenclamide on 8th, 15th and 22nd day. While aqueous and Methanolic extracts produced significant reduction in FBGL. Glibenclamide (10mg/kg) showed ($P < 0.05$) significant suppression in FBGL rise at first half-an-hour, 1hr and normalized FBGL within 2hr. The detailed results are summarized in Table No.

Table No: 7.11- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 8th, 15th and 22nd day in Diabetic rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level(mg/dl)		
		8 th day	15 th day	22 nd day
Normal control	-	85.05±3.63	83.50±2.87	84.99±1.58
Diabetic control	10	284.11±02.69	272.01±19.55	320.57±14.99
Glibenclamide	10	361.18±21.10	310.18±11.73	286.41±18.55
AQEDP1	20	258.06±10.62	240.00±16.40	202.36±11.90
AQEDP2	30	285.24±13.30	278.68±13.78	251.98±19.75
MEDP1	20	260.02±12.11	220.26±17.87	185.63±17.99
MEDP2	30	352.15±14.61	325.16±15.28	267.66±10.86

Values are expressed as mean ± S.E.M. n=6. Significant values were compared with $P < 0.05$. Normal control Vs all groups. Paranthesis indicates % reduction in BGL.

Figure: 7.10- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 8th, 15th and 22nd day in Diabetic rats.

Table No: 7.12- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 8th day in Diabetic rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level (mg/dl) 8 th day			
		0.5 hour	1 st hour	1.5 hour	2 nd hour
Normal control	-	50.18±2.69	61.20±2.19	72.18±2.90	85.75±3.63
Diabetic control	10	191.05±15.72	202.96±18.57	242.12±10.13	281.01±02.69
Glibenclamide	10	182.11±21.51	241.28±21.05	300.12±15.26	360.38±21.10
AQEDP1	20	178.52±31.26	189.56±24.81	215.20±10.63	266.26±10.62
AQEDP2	30	167.46±21.51	180.06±54.43	245.88±21.35	277.14±13.30
MEDP1	20	160.13±14.10	162.48±02.05	220.51±05.19	258.22±12.11
MEDP2	30	150.92±21.53	201.92±10.35	278.39±13.73	350.55±14.61

Figure: 7.11- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 8th day in Diabetic rats

Table No: 7.13- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 15th day in Diabetic rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level (mg/dl) 15 th day			
		0.5 hour	1 st hour	1.5 hour	2 nd hour
Normal control	-	50.01±1.71	58.26±3.19	72.15±1.54	84.59±2.87
Diabetic control	10	184.26±1.72	200.06±1.79	221.26±12.63	275.00±19.55
Glibenclamide	10	191.16±1.34	270.66±6.12	311.28±11.31	312.88±11.73
AQEDP1	20	156.51±6.10	201.02±0.89	230.31±15.73	241.70±16.40
AQEDP2	30	180.70±1.62	192.15±3.10	270.02±01.16	280.78±13.78
MEDP1	20	145.15±1.75	181.39±1.13	228.15±1.25	221.56±17.87
MEDP2	30	178.18±5.96	253.15±5.01	289.11±36.12	330.76±15.28

Figure: 7.12- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 15th day in Diabetic rats.

Table No: 7.15- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 22nd day in Diabetic rats.

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Blood glucose level (mg/dl) 22 nd day			
		0.5 hour	1 st hour	1.5 hour	2 nd hour
Normal control	-	61.25±0.51	66.3±2.05	83.52±3.96	90.99±1.58
Diabetic control	10	203.15±02.36	232.25±50.18	281.18±33.25	321.57±14.99
Glibenclamide	10	163.89±3.46	212.72±23.03	253.19±13.06	289.41±18.55
AQEDP1	20	143.41±53.09	169.22±26.17	183.56±53.36	208.36±11.90
AQEDP2	30	159.59±08.18	199.17±39.02	263.11±06.19	255.98±19.75
MEDP1	20	141.11±14.07	162.89±3.52	180.73±2.65	188.63±17.99
MEDP2	30	154.17±08.10	182.14±02.01	225.63±14.25	270.66±10.86

Figure: 7.13- Effect of extracts of *Diospyros peregrine* on 22nd day in Diabetic rats

DISCUSSION:

Despite the fact that diabetes has high prevalence, morbidity and mortality globally, it is regarded as non curable but controllable disease. Different synthetic drugs, plant remedies and dietary modification play an effective role in the reduction of the suffering that it causes. The potential role of medicinal plants as

antidiabetic agents has been reviewed by several authors. In order to identify the plants with antidiabetic properties various plants have been tested *in-vivo* using animal models, for example rats, against the complications caused by inducers of diabetes, and it has been established that many plants possess the potential to lower the fasting blood glucose levels and

besides help in improving other diabetic complications. The sustained reduction in hyperglycemia automatically decreases the risk of other major complications of diabetes. Effective glucose control is the key for preventing or reversing the diabetic complications and improving the quality of life of the diabetics.

Phytochemical analysis of extracts of leaves of *Diospyros peregrine* revealed the presence of secondary metabolites that have been shown to possess antidiabetic effect in other plants. Flavonoids, alkaloids and Steroids which were responsible for the antidiabetic effect in other plants were also detected in the extracts of this plant. The presence of phenols in the plant could also be responsible for the antidiabetic effect have been shown to prevent the destruction of β -cells by inhibiting the peroxidation chain reaction and thus they may provide protection against the development of diabetes. Extracts of leaves of *Diospyros peregrine* appear to be attractive materials for further studies leading to possible drug development for diabetes. Development of phytomedicines is relatively inexpensive and less time consuming; it is more suited to our economic conditions than allopathic drug development which is more expensive and spread over several years.

CONCLUSION:

The study was performed to find out the beneficial effects of two different extracts of leaves of *Diospyros peregrine* in normoglycaemic rats and streptozotocin (STZ) induced diabetic rats and the results reveal that the plant has beneficial effects on blood glucose levels. In current scenario, herbs are the potent sources of medicines used in the treatment of various disease and disorders. Since, plants are used as medicine there is prompt need of evaluation of plant species, therefore, the present work was conceived to evaluate the phytochemical and pharmacological screening of leaves of *Diospyros peregrine*. The Phytochemical evaluation has revealed the presence of Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Steroids, Tannins, Anthraquinones, Terpenoids, Cardiac glycoside.

The data of the blood glucose level of rats treated with streptozotocin (STZ) (150mg/kg body weight) produced diabetes within 72 hours. After 72 hours of streptozotocin (STZ) administered the blood glucose levels of rats were observed. It was observed that significant lowering of sugar in aqueous and Methanolic extract. The administration of different extracts at a dose of 20 and 30 mg/kg showed significant anti-hyperglycemic effect at 22nd day which was evident from the 7th day on wards as

compared to standard. The aqueous and Methanolic extract of *Diospyros peregrine* has showed better anti-hyperglycemic effect of the extract on the fasting blood sugar levels on diabetic rats are shown in table. The decreasing blood glucose levels are comparable with that of 10 mg/kg of Glibenclamide. The Glibenclamide (10 mg/kg body weight) shows significant effect on compare to the initial and more significant effect on the 22nd Day compare to the initial. The aqueous and Methanolic extracts of 20 and 30mg/kg body weight shows significant ($P^* < 0.05$), effect.

FUTURE SCOPE

The current thesis revealed the antidiabetic potential of *Diospyros peregrine* being effective in hyperglycemia and their ability to protect against other metabolic aberrations caused by diabetes in rats, which seems to validate its therapeutic traditional use. The antidiabetic effect of *Diospyros peregrine* may be due to their ability to increase the number and restore the integrity of pancreatic β -cells of islets of Langerhans. However further studies are required to evaluate other chemical constituents of the plant for their hypoglycemic potential and to identify their target/s, mechanism of action and combination of plant products with synthetic drugs.

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